

THEORIES OF INVESTIGATING LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN SPIRITUAL STATE IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6548144>

Urolov Bakhrom

master, Uzbekistan State World Language University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Akhmedov Oybek

doctor of philological sciences (DSc), Uzbekistan State World Language University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation. *Emotions are specific forms of interaction of a human being and environment. They help us to cognate the world and define our place in it. Linguistics of emotions (emotiology) usually defines "emotion" as the form of world reflection in human conscience to denote some mental experience, commotion and feeling. Emotions are closely connected with culture. So that we can relate it with lingua-culturology. Their role in culture and significance of the culture in formation and conceptualization of emotions is enormous.*

Keywords: *emotions; feelings; sadness; linguistic; cognitive appraisal; action; physiological changes.*

Emotions are colorful, dramatic, fascinating, and essential dimensions of every person's experience. These primitive mechanisms send a constant stream of powerful signals that can guide us along the difficult path of survival, or quickly send us off on destructive and painful tangents. How well do you understand these essential and universal signals? Many believe that living life to its fullest requires experiencing and enjoying the full range of human emotions. Yet so many of us are uncomfortable with emotions; we don't recognize what they are, what they are telling us, how they can be helpful, or the choices we have in how to respond to them. Many of us were taught to ignore, suppress, diminish, or deny our own subtle feelings and vivid passions. Do you know how you feel? What emotions can you recognize and describe? We may have mistakenly learned to overreact to various negative emotions while suppressing positive ones. Unfortunately some of us are prisoners of anger, hate, guilt, sadness, fear, anxiety, shame, humiliation, envy, pain, and violence without understanding what has consumed so much of our lives. Others endure a lonely and sterile existence without experiencing genuine feelings or passionate emotions.

But passion has logic. Emotions obey their own peculiar rules that we can study, understand, listen to, learn from, master, and even enjoy. How well can you interpret what your emotions are telling you? The purpose of this investigation is to analyze and make constructive decisions based on the information emotions provide. Constructive and authentic human interactions become possible. People have to listen carefully to what your emotions are telling them.

Some would say: not “feelings” (sezgi, tuyg’u), but “emotions” (his-hayajon, ruhiy kechinma) – and the question “which of the two (feelings or emotions)” plunges us straight into the heart of the central controversy concerning the relationship between human biology on the one hand and language and culture on the other. Many psychologists and linguists appear to be more comfortable with the term “emotion” than “feeling” because “emotions” seem to be somehow “objective”. It is often assumed that only the “objective” is real and amenable to rigorous study, and that “emotions” have a biological foundation and can therefore be studied “objectively”, whereas feelings cannot be studied at all calls this attitude “the flight from subjectivity”. Seventy years ago the founder of behaviourism John Watson proposed the following definition “An emotion is an hereditary ‘pattern-reaction’ involving profound changes of the bodily mechanisms as a whole, but particularly of the visceral and glandular systems”. While such behaviorist conceptions of “emotions” have now been repudiated, “emotions” are still seen as something that, for example, can be measured. [1] Plutchik himself writes: “Because emotions are complex states of the organism involving feelings, behaviour, impulses, physiological changes and efforts at control, the measurement of emotions is also a complex process”.

Piece of the difficulty is because our experiences are so complex and involve so many various factors, so varying one emotion from another is a lot like drawing lines of water in the ocean. It could be difficult to determine where one emotions ends or another begins. Even when we analyze a commonsense emotion like “happiness” or “fear”, we know from everyday experience that these emotions come in many different degrees, qualities, and intensities. In addition to this idea, our experiences are often comprised of multiple emotions at once, which add another dimension of complexity to our emotional experience.

In the beginning of XIX century V. Humboldt noticed that language is penetrated by feelings as an activity of the person. Now the linguistics has addressed again to the theory of V. Humboldt and began to study

language in a close connection with the person. At all times people experienced, experience and will experience the same feelings: pleasure (huzur-halovat), grief (g'amandux), love (sevgi), sadness (xafalik)... Huge emotional experience is stored.

Uniqueness of emotions is compared with other objects of nomination, first of all it is found out in variety and richness of language that means their expression which include and correspond lexicon, phraseological syntactic constructions, special intonation, and a word order. The dominant role belongs to lexicon. And in lexical set, in participating and in a designation of emotions, words which belong to different parts of speech (nouns, verbs, adjective, adverbs, words of a category of condition, an interjection). Lazarus' theory is very influential; emotion is a disturbance that occurs in the following order:

Cognitive appraisal–The individual assesses the event cognitively, which cues the emotion.

Physiological changes–The cognitive reaction starts biological changes such as increased heart rate or pituitary adrenal response.

Action–The individual feels the emotion and chooses how to react.

For example: Jenny sees a snake–Jenni ilonni ko'rdi Jenny cognitively assesses the snake in her presence. Cognition allows her to understand it as a danger. Her brain activates Adrenaline gland which pumps Adrenaline through her blood stream resulting in increased heartbeat. Jenny screams and runs away. Lazarus stressed that the quality and intensity of emotions are controlled through cognitive processes. These processes underline coping strategies that form the emotional reaction by altering the relationship between the person and the environment. [2] Lazarus expressed the position of human very clearly. These example may show that we can easily express emotions and feelings in the language.

Expressiveness as an aspect of the semantics of the word has some components that can be qualified as obligatory connotative semes fully or partially realized in speech: intensity score, imagery, emotiveness. [3] Thus, expressiveness as a semasiological category which has pragmatic aspect of operation based on the consideration of choice; expressiveness is determined in opposition to the neutral component realized in human speech. This understanding of expressiveness as a result of the use of emotional language units in speech explains its synonymy with the concept of intensity. Note also that many linguists have identified emotional and expressive functions of language. Thus, in the writings of R. Jakobson one can find the statement that the expressive / emotional

function (emotive function) is intended to express the attitude of the speaker to the action. However, there is a different point of view that expressive function is associated with the expression of thought – an idea, which was initially produced by V. Avrorin while distinguishing features of language and speech. The researcher differs expressive function of language along with communicative, constructive (the function of forming opinions) and cumulative (accumulation of social experience and knowledge) ones.

The problem in the linguistic aspect of lexical units expressing human spiritual state and emotions begins with the problem of language functions -functions and induce expression of emotions in the process of verbal communication. Emotion word (French "emotnon", Lat. "Emovere" "excite", "worry") refers to psychic experience, excitement, feelings, for example *anger, fear, love, contempt, etc.*

A word generalizes (signifying function), means (the nominative function), expresses attitudes, feelings of a speaker and a listener (emotive function). In the latter case there is no nomination emotive end in itself but a lexical unit can transfer the thought of them and their emotional relationship: *Headstrong, to cachinnate (laugh at people), tattle, bloke, fantastic, beastly, etc.*

Many modern theories of emotions are the key concepts of excitation (arousal) and evaluation (appraisal). As it is clear from the very terms, the first one reflects the physiological, natural essence of emotion, while the second involves some degree of mental processing of emotional events. Analyzing views of various researchers on the relation of emotional and rational emotions, A. Orthon and A. Collins Klour note that psychologists rarely acknowledge that knowledge plays an important role in relation to emotions, but most of them did not put forward any detailed assumptions about how it happens. However, as the authors point out, one of the most clearer explanations given Mandler [55] which argues that the assessment of the content is the "cold" part of the emotions, while the "hot" part is generated by the excitation [4].

Rejecting applied in many psychological studies following the concept of basic emotions (usually understood to 5-6 "vital", the most common and early manifested emotions such as *fear, anger, joy, love, happiness*), these authors base their theory of emotions by identifying different concepts that a person uses when assessing situations of emotions. This estimate is based on the concept in their desirability, approval

sequences that apply to emotions, based on the event, agent and object, respectively.

Nowadays modern linguistic theories treat referential meaning as primary. It is a rather hard-earned blindness, given how much of the language around us is emotive or expressive. And earlier linguistic theories gave a prominent role for the emotive/expressive aspects of language. It allows, as in Jakobson, R. Linguistics and poetics [5] a distinction between message-orientation, speaker-orientation, and listener-orientation. Till nowadays these are probably some mistakes to try to divide these. There is no an expression of inner states that doesn't influence listeners and there are no purely representational, non-social uses of signs. Meaning isn't determined by holding sentences up and proving their truth conditions. It can be achieved collaboratively over the course of an interaction. These interactions aren't a game. Pragmaticists can get this right with speech acts and sociolinguists get this right when they speak about style and construction, but most linguists stay on safer shores where facts are solid and avoid a "certain swerving".

Two components of emotiveness can be as a functional semantic category, the leading feature of which is the expression and transmission of emotions:

- 1) emotiveness as a pragmatic constant of language and speech related to the subjective attitude of a speaker to an object of evaluation (always expressive);
- 2) emotiveness as a component of connotative semantics of words, expressions, texts.

Components defined onto logically differ from each other: if emotiveness of the first type is always associated with functional-semantic categories and subjective evaluation modality, the emotiveness of the second type has a character and may be actualized directly or neutralized in the speech context. [6]

All science studies this psychological phenomenon: psychology, physiology, sociology, philosophy, ethics, medicine, cybernetics, biochemistry, linguistics, literary criticism. Psychological and psycholinguistic sciences are aimed at, first of all, research of emotion functions in activity of the person.

Expressive and emotive function – they are functional units of language, they are caused by different types of values of linguistic units: emotive and expressive. In the words of valuation prevails axiological function, while descriptive - nominative. This allows us to offer that language

has not all of these functions. This function is a function of its units. Distinction emotive and expressive functions of speech is necessary for understanding the various purposes of different semantic types of words, particularly for differentiating emotive and expressive vocabulary in all languages constructions. And this, in turn, it is possible to understand the functions of expressing text and their interaction in different types of texts. Emotive function of the language is considered to be one of the speech functions, attributed to such speech functions as signal, nominative, poetic, ethnic and magic. In our opinion, speech nature of the category of emotiveness is beyond doubt as there are different usage levels language tools, which are inherent from emotiveness. This consideration supports V. Shakhovskij describing the emotional component of meaning as "such a semantic part, through which linguistic unit realizes its emotional function" [7].

Terminological differences can be observed also when emotional function of linguistic units promoting formation of emotional speech act, becomes known as emotional - expressive, as in the quotation: "The leading means of expressing emotions in speech is intonation" [7].

At the present stage of the study of our research work this is possible to detect in the lexicon of emotions the following research areas:

- 1) the study of individual emotive tokens;
- 2) study of lexical and semantic groups emotive lexical units;
- 3) study of synonymous and antonymous relations of emotive lexicon;
- 4) study of semantic / thematic fields covering emotive language;
- 5) criteria emotive language and its characters;
- 6) the ratio of linguistics and paralinguistic emotions;

REFERENCES:

1. Oatley K. Emotions: a brief history. – USA; UK; Australia: Blackwell publishing. P. 190.
2. Oxford advanced learners dictionary of current English / A.S Hornby with A.P. Cowie A.C Gimson: Oxford University press, 2009.
3. Johnson-Laird P. N & Keith Oatley. The Language of Emotions: An Analysis of a Semantic Field Cognition And Emotion, 1989. P. 81–123.
4. Shakhovskij V. Types of Emotive Vocabulary //Questions of General Linguistics. – 1994. № 1. P. 20 – 25.
5. Shumeiko O. Semantics of lexical units that denote negative emotions in modern American English, The Advanced Science Journal, Volume 2011 Issue 1. P. 7–10.

6. *Solomon R. C.* The Philosophy of Emotions // Handbook of Emotions. Edited by M. Lewis and J. M. Haviland. New York; London: The Guilford Press, 1993. P. 3–16.

7. *Stearns P. N.* History of Emotions: The Issue of Change // Handbook of Emotions. Edited by M. Lewis and J. M. Haviland. New York; London: The Guilford Press, 1993. P. 17–28.